

ARDC Co-Investment Guidelines

Date Effective	12 November 2025
Review Date	12 November 2027
Type	Guidelines
Owner	Chief Operating Officer
Approved by	Chief Executive Officer
Category	Operations and Projects
Version Number	2.2
Audience	External
Content Enquiries	ops@ardc.edu.au
Related Documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ NCRIS 2025 Guidelines ■ 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap ■ 2026 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap
Purpose	<p>This document provides guidance for project partners contributing to ARDC co-investment projects. It outlines expectations for cash and in-kind contributions and addresses common questions regarding project reporting and eligibility. Any specific questions related to project co-investment reporting should be directed to ops@ardc.edu.au.</p>

1. Strategic Requirements for Co-Investment

Under the National Research Infrastructure (NRI) Investment Principles outlined in the *2021 Research Infrastructure Roadmap*, all investments are expected to encourage and leverage co-investment from Commonwealth, state and territory governments, universities, and the public and private sectors.

Co-investment is a critical contributor to project success. It reflects partner commitment to accessing and sustaining world-class research infrastructure and helps demonstrate the sector's collective support to governments. These contributions ensure that project outcomes are mutually beneficial and impactful, aligning with ARDC's strategic investment priorities.

The ARDC seeks to foster long-term partnerships through co-investment, where both ARDC and its partners contribute resources, expertise, and sustained effort beyond the initial funding. As an NCRIS-funded capability, ARDC seeks a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio—attracting a minimum of \$1 of eligible partner co-investment for every \$1 of NCRIS funding received.

However, ARDC recognises that partner constraints might require flexibility in our approach to co-investment. Reductions in co-investment will be considered by exception, taking into account partner circumstances and project value.

Key Requirements

Requirement	Detail
Minimum 1:1 Co-Investment Ratio	Partners should match ARDC investment with equal value of cash and/or in-kind support, with flexibility for exceptional circumstances.
Planning	All contributions must be agreed during project setup in consultation with ARDC.
Eligibility	Contributions must align with 2025 NCRIS Guidelines and support project objectives.
Financial Reporting	Annual and final (whole-of-life) financial acquittals will be required.
Validation	All contributions must be documented and verifiable. Satisfactory written evidence of contributions can be requested by the ARDC as per Schedule 2, Item 3 'Other

	Contributions' of ARDC's standard subcontractor agreement.
--	--

2. ARDC Investment Principles in Projects

At the ARDC, we support Australia’s research and innovation ecosystem by enabling excellence in the creation, analysis, and retention of high-quality data assets.

ARDC co-investment projects:

- Have a defined start and end date
- Contain agreed deliverables aligned with ARDC strategy
- Have a minimum level of partner co-investment (1:1 ratio, with flexibility for exceptional circumstances).

ARDC’s contribution is partly in the form of cash investment, which may only be applied to eligible activities as defined by the 2025 NCRIS Guidelines. These eligibility criteria may be updated by the government over time. In addition, ARDC’s contribution will also include a range of technical, program and project management, expertise and operational staff to support the successful delivery of the project.

3. Eligible Partner Co-Investment

Partner co-investment may be provided as **cash**, **in-kind**, or a **combination of both**. All contributions must be agreed upon during the project planning stage in consultation with ARDC staff. It is the responsibility of each contributing organisation to ensure compliance with any relevant funding rules.

Type	Definition
Cash Co-Investment	Direct financial contributions where actual money leaves the contributing organisation to support the project. Must be validated and acquitted.
In-Kind Co-Investment	Non-cash resources that directly support the project's delivery and objectives. Must be validated and acquitted.

Partners must provide an **annual and final (whole of life) acquitted financial statement** through to the end of the project which includes reporting on all forms of co-investment.

Cash Co-Investment

Definition: Direct financial contributions where actual money leaves the contributing organisation to support the project.

Examples include:

- **External contractor payments:** The partner pays a consulting firm or external advisor directly to deliver project outputs
- **Staffing costs:** An institution pays the salary costs for a staff member seconded full-time to a co-investment project
- **Equipment or resource purchases:** Partner purchases equipment, software licenses, or other resources specifically for the project
- **Pre-approved travel allowances:** Partner pays for staff travel and accommodation related to project delivery and included in the approved project budget

Requirements:

- Must be relevant to the project
- Must be reportable and verifiable
- Must be supported by evidence upon request
- Must be included in annual and final acquitted financial statements

In-Kind Co-Investment

Definition: Non-cash resources that directly support the project's delivery and objectives.

Examples include:

- **Staff time:** Existing staff contributing a fraction of their time to the project as part of their regular duties
- **Use of equipment or facilities:** Access to existing infrastructure, laboratories, or computational resources
- **Administrative or technical services:** Support provided by existing institutional staff

Requirements:

- Must be relevant to eligible project activities
- Must be documented and able to be validated
- Must be included in annual acquitted financial statements

4. Reporting Co-Investment Contributions

Partners must provide comprehensive reporting on all co-investment contributions through:

- Annual financial acquittals
- A whole-of-life final acquittal due two months after project end date

Reporting Flexibility and Thresholds

Recognising the administrative burden of reporting small contributions across multiple partners, ARDC applies the following principles:

- No annual minimums: Co-investment contributions can occur at any time over the project lifecycle
- Project-level compliance: If agreed co-investment is not achieved during a specific reporting period, no variation is required as long as the full commitment is met by the end of the project
- Threshold consideration: For contributions below 10% of the total contract value, ARDC may consider administrative efficiency and work with partners to determine the most appropriate reporting approach

Validation

Co-investment must be validated and ARDC reserves the right to request clarification or supporting documentation at any time. All contributions must be documented and verifiable.

5. Post-Project Impact Tracking

The ARDC collects and reports on the uptake and adoption of national scale infrastructure, standards, frameworks and models, skills and training, and policy and strategy contributions delivered via its co-investment projects and programs.

ARDC tracks ongoing outcomes through post-project reporting. While ARDC cannot enforce reporting obligations beyond a project's contracted end date, partners are requested to continue contributing to reporting and impact assessments to demonstrate the ongoing success and delivery of national scale infrastructures and services. This is critical to highlight the need for ongoing government and industry investment in NCRIS.

6. Flexibility and Exceptions

ARDC recognises that partner circumstances might change during project lifecycles. We are committed to working collaboratively with partners to:

- **Address partner constraints** that might affect co-investment capacity
- **Consider exceptional circumstances** that may warrant adjustments to co-investment requirements
- **Maintain project value** while balancing administrative efficiency with accountability requirements

Partners experiencing difficulties meeting co-investment commitments should contact the ARDC Contracts team early to discuss potential solutions.

For questions related to co-investment planning or reporting, contact:

contracts@ardc.edu.au